

COPING STRATEGIES AMONG ADOLESCENT STUDENTS: INSIGHTS FROM A SCHOOL-BASED SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence is a critical developmental stage marked by rapid physical, emotional, and social changes, making individuals particularly vulnerable to stress arising from academic demands, family expectations, and social relationships. Ineffective stress management during this period may lead to adverse psychological and educational outcomes. The present study aimed to examine the coping strategies employed by adolescent students in managing stress. A descriptive survey method was adopted, and data were collected from a sample of 300 ninth-grade students (150 boys and 150 girls) drawn through stratified random sampling from eight government and private secondary schools in Amritsar city. The Coping Strategies Scale developed by Freedenberg and Lewis (2011) was used as the research instrument. Percentage analysis was employed to analyze the data.

The findings revealed that adolescents predominantly used coping strategies such as social support, work-oriented coping, problem-solving, worry management, and social action, reporting their use often or very often across most domains. Recreational and relaxation strategies, including physical activity and humor, were also widely adopted. However, the utilization of professional help was comparatively low, and the presence of maladaptive strategies such as avoidance and ignoring stressors was observed among a notable proportion of students.

The results indicate that while adolescents largely rely on adaptive coping mechanisms, there remains a need to strengthen awareness, accessibility, and acceptance of professional support services. The study highlights the importance of school-based interventions, counseling services, and supportive educational environments to promote healthy coping strategies and enhance adolescents' psychological well-being and academic adjustment.

Keywords: Adolescents, Stress, Coping Strategies, Academic Stress, Mental Well-being

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a critical developmental stage characterized by significant physical, emotional, and social changes. During this period, individuals often face various stressors, such as academic

pressure, peer relationships, family dynamics, and societal expectations, all of which can lead to heightened stress levels. “Stress, if not managed effectively, can result in various negative outcomes, including anxiety, depression, poor academic performance, and even substance abuse” (Compas et al., 2017). Stress is a condition of anxiety or tension brought on by a challenging circumstance. Stress is a normal human reaction that forces us to confront obstacles and dangers in our lives. Stress affects everyone to some extent. But how we handle stress has a significant impact on our general health (WHO, 2023). A "pain in the chest or in the pit of the stomach or in the form of clenching their jaws" is one symptom that some people may encounter (Murberg, 2005). Every person occasionally encounters stress. Situations like transferring to a new institution, taking tests, interacting with friends and classmates, when friends are ill, parental divorce or separation, and the death of a loved one can all cause stress for students.

Stress has become an unavoidable aspect of students' lives and the lives of those who are connected to them in the academic setting. Adolescent parents must manage both their own and their children's academic stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Thus, a primary goal of psychological and educational research is to comprehend the nature of stress and how it affects teenage wellbeing. Adolescence is therefore a time when people are more susceptible to stress because it is a time of tremendous physical, emotional, and cognitive growth (WHO, 2023). The types of stress that adolescents encounter can vary greatly, depending on the nature of the stressor, its duration, and how the adolescent perceives and responds to it. The following are common types of stress experienced by adolescents:

- **Academic stress** is one of the most prevalent types of stress among adolescents, stemming from school-related pressures such as academic performance, exams, homework, and meeting expectations set by parents or teachers. “Adolescents often experience high levels of stress due to the fear of failure, competition with peers, and concerns about future educational and career prospects” (Fletcher et al., 2018). This form of stress can affect cognitive functioning, emotional regulation, and overall well-being, “leading to anxiety and burnout if not managed effectively” (Suldo et al., 2014).
- **Family Stress** are also significant during adolescence. These can include conflicts with parents or siblings, divorce, financial instability, or the pressure to meet family expectations. Adolescents might struggle with their evolving roles within the family, such as seeking independence while maintaining family connections. “Family stress can impact an adolescent’s emotional health, contributing to feelings of confusion, anxiety, or resentment” (Loeber et al., 2014). In cases of dysfunctional family dynamics or parental neglect, “family stress can exacerbate the risk for mental health issues such as depression or substance abuse” (McMahon et al., 2018).

Figure: 1 Types of Stress (Laldikpuii, & Vijayan, 2023).

- **“Social stress** refers to stress related to relationships with peers, family members, and others in the adolescent's social environment”. Peer pressure, bullying, social media interactions, and struggles to form or maintain friendships are common sources of social stress. “Adolescents often face the challenge of balancing their desire for independence with their need for social acceptance, leading to stress in their social lives” (Seiffge-Krenke, 2011). In particular, “the rise of social media has introduced new pressures, such as the need for constant validation or fear of social exclusion” (Fuchs & Kimmerle, 2019).

Recent studies have highlighted that “adolescents experience unique stressors that are often compounded by the developmental tasks they must navigate, such as identity formation, autonomy, and future planning” (Steinberg, 2020). “The increasing demands of academic achievement and extracurricular involvement, as well as challenges such as bullying and social media pressures, contribute to the stress levels reported by young people” (Gore et al., 2021). Furthermore, “the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these stressors, affecting adolescents' social interactions and mental health, leading to increased feelings of isolation, uncertainty, and fear” (Loades et al., 2020). All areas of psychology—health, psychology, environmental psychology, developmental psychology, neuropsychology, organisational behaviour, clinical psychology, etc.—address stress and coping mechanisms. Today's students studying in a competitive academic setting face a variety of pressures from life changes related to personal aspirations, the need to succeed, and meeting university, family, and community expectations. These experiences have an impact on how they manage on a daily basis. In stress-related literature, the term “coping” is understood in two distinct ways. It has been used to denote “the

way of dealing with stress or effort to master conditions of harm, threat, or challenge when a routine or automatic response is not readily available” (Pillai & Jose, 2023). Coping refers to mastering conditions that exceed adaptive resources. Lazarus emphasized “the key role of cognitive process in coping activities and the importance of coping in determination of quality and intensity of emotional reactions to stress”.

To cope with stress, adolescents employ various coping strategies that can be broadly categorized into problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies. “Problem-focused coping involves direct actions to address or resolve the stressor, while emotion-focused coping involves regulating emotional responses to the stressor” (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980). “The effectiveness of these coping strategies varies, and maladaptive coping mechanisms, such as avoidance or substance use, can further exacerbate stress and lead to negative mental health outcomes”(Zimmerman et al., 2018). So, “adaptive coping mechanisms during adolescence is crucial for promoting resilience and mitigating the negative effects of stress” (Rosen et al., 2018). “Social support, positive reappraisal, and mindfulness-based interventions have shown promise in helping adolescents manage stress effectively” (Eisenberg et al., 2020). Therefore, it is essential to not only understand the stressors that adolescents face but also to explore the coping strategies they use, to inform interventions and programs that can enhance their coping skills and overall well-being.

A comprehensive review of literature on stress and coping strategies among adolescent students reveals significant findings across various regions and contexts. Below is a synthesis of key studies, categorized by thematic focus:

(Parikh et al., 2019) explored stress and coping among urban school-going adolescents in India, identifying academic pressure, peer relationships, and parental expectations as primary stressors. The study found that emotion-focused coping strategies were more commonly employed than problem-focused strategies. Other important study of Laldikpuii & Vijayan(2023) examined higher secondary students in Mizoram, India, revealing that academic stress negatively impacts mental well-being. Their findings underscore the importance of developing gender-sensitive interventions to address stress and promote mental well-being among students. Then, Sreekanth et al. (2023) reported that 76% of high school adolescents experienced stress, with avoidance coping strategies being predominant. The study highlighted the significant influence of family and educational institution factors on stress levels. One more important study of Schleider (2024) advocated for the integration of resilience interventions, such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and mindfulness, into educational curricula. The article emphasized that voluntary participation in these programs yields better outcomes, suggesting the importance of tailored and accessible resources for adolescents. Morin (2024) provided an overview of coping skills for adolescents, categorizing them into emotion-focused and problem-focused strategies. The article recommended techniques such as mindfulness, exercise, and positive self-talk to manage stress effectively. Other study of Carl, Jay and Luzano (2024) conducted a systematic review highlighting that academic stress among high school students adversely affects their

mental health and academic performance. They identified emotion-focused coping strategies, such as seeking emotional support, as prevalent among students. The study emphasized the need for educational interventions to foster adaptive coping mechanisms.

These studies collectively underscore the multifaceted nature of stress among adolescents and the diverse coping strategies employed. They highlight the importance of culturally sensitive, context-specific interventions to support adolescent mental health effectively. Despite extensive research on stress and coping strategies among adolescents, several gaps remain. Many studies lack cultural contextualization, with limited exploration of how cultural and religious factors influence coping, particularly in non-Western settings. Gender-specific coping mechanisms are under-researched, with few studies offering a detailed comparison between how male and female adolescents manage stress. The growing influence of digital stressors, such as social media and cyberbullying, is not sufficiently addressed. Additionally, most existing research is cross-sectional, lacking longitudinal insights into how coping strategies evolve over time. While the COVID-19 pandemic has prompted new studies, long-term effects on adolescent mental health and the effectiveness of newly introduced interventions remain unclear. Furthermore, there is a shortage of evaluations on the implementation and scalability of school-based coping programs, especially in under-resourced areas.

OBJECTIVE

- To study the Coping Strategies among Adolescent students.

TOOL USED

Coping Strategies scale by Freedenberg and Lewis (2011).

2. METHOD OF THE STUDY

The study falls under the domain of descriptive research and survey method has been used to collect data.

Sampling Technique

Stratified random sampling has been used in this investigation. With this method, every unit in the sample has an equal chance of being selected and included in the sample. The choice of one person or unit does not in any way depend on the choice of another person or unit. All ninth-grade private and secondary school pupils enrolled in various Amritsar city schools made up the study's population. Eight schools were chosen at random. For the study, 300 ninth-grade students from eight randomly chosen public and private schools—150 boys and 150 girls—were sampled.

Analysis and Interpretation

TABLE 1

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF DIMENSIONS OF COPING STRATEGIES AMONG ADOLESCENTS

Domains of coping strategies	NEVER (In %)	RARELY (In %)	SOMETIMES (In %)	OFTEN (In %)	VERY OFTEN (In %)
Social Support	4	8	15	50	23
Work Dimension	3	7	15	49	26
Worry Dimension	4	8	9	52	27
Wishful Thinking	3	7	20	50	20
Social Action	3	7	15	50	25
Self-Blame	3	7	15	52	23
Self-Strategy	3	7	20	40	30
Spirit	3	7	17	49	24
Focus on the Positive	3	8	19	47	23
Self-Professional Help	5	9	26	29	31
Relax Dimension	3	10	29	38	20
Physical Recreation	3	8	15	45	29
Act up Dimension	3	7	20	48	22
Humour Dimension	4	10	19	45	22
Not Cope Dimension	3	8	19	45	25
Accept Dimension	3	8	19	45	25
Ignore Dimension	3	8	20	46	23
Friends Dimension	3	8	31	34	24
Solving Problem	4	8	16	48	24
Tension Reduction	8	8	20	50	14

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The percentage analysis of coping strategies (Table 1) revealed that adolescents predominantly reported using coping strategies “often” and “very often” across most domains. The highest reported strategies included worry dimension (52% often, 27% very often), work dimension (49% often, 26% very often), and social support (50% often, 23% very often). Similarly, problem-solving (48% often, 24% very often), self-blame (52% often, 23% very often), and social action (50% often, 25% very often) were also frequently employed.

Leisure and relaxation-based strategies such as physical recreation (45% often, 29% very often), humour (45% often, 22% very often), and relax dimension (38% often, 20% very often) were reported by a majority of students, underscoring the significance of recreational outlets in managing stress.

In contrast, the strategy of self-professional help received comparatively lower responses, with

only 29% indicating often and 31% very often, suggesting that adolescents are less inclined to approach counselors or professionals when coping with stress. Maladaptive patterns such as not coping (45% often, 25% very often) and ignoring stressors (46% often, 23% very often) were also present, though to a lesser extent than adaptive strategies.

Discussion

Predominance of Adaptive Coping

The results indicate that adolescents largely prefer adaptive coping strategies, including social support, problem-solving, and focusing on the positive. This aligns with previous research which shows that “adolescents tend to rely on constructive methods that foster resilience and well-being” (Compas et al., 2017; Rosen et al., 2018). Such strategies help students maintain balance between academic demands and personal challenges.

Role of Social and Interpersonal Support

Social support (73% combined often/very often) and friends’ support (58%) emerged as critical resources. This is consistent with findings by Zammuner (2019), who reported that “seeking social support and problem-solving were associated with lower social loneliness and higher life satisfaction among adolescents”. Similarly, Mmari & Mafuta (2024) found that “during the COVID-19 pandemic, support from family and peers was the most common and effective coping mechanism”. These findings confirm that strong social connections act as protective factors against stress.

Cognitive and Emotional Regulation

Cognitive strategies such as wishful thinking (70%), self-blame (75%), and focusing on the positive (70%) reflect adolescents’ attempts to regulate emotions internally. “While positive reframing is adaptive, reliance on self-blame may increase vulnerability to depressive symptoms”, as suggested by Murberg (2005). Similarly, Everall, Altrows, & Paulson (2006) highlighted that “emotional coping could become maladaptive if not paired with constructive outlets”. Thus, while emotional regulation is widely used, its impact varies depending on whether strategies are adaptive (positive focus) or maladaptive (self-blame).

Active, Problem-Focused Approaches

Problem-solving (72% combined often/very often) and work-related coping (75%) highlight adolescents’ reliance on proactive coping. This reflects findings from Pillai & Jose (2023), who observed that “adolescents frequently used problem-focused strategies to handle academic pressures”. Similarly, Zaafer (2022) reported that “girls were more likely than boys to use adaptive strategies such as problem-solving and cognitive restructuring”. These results suggest that adolescents’ tendency toward problem-oriented coping supports resilience and academic persistence.

Recreation and Humor as Stress Buffers

Physical recreation (74%), humor (67%), and relaxation (58%) were also significant outlets. These results are in line with Morin (2024), who recommended “exercise, humor, and mindfulness as effective strategies for adolescents to manage stress”. Engaging in sports, hobbies, and cultural activities therefore not only relieves tension but also contributes to better emotional well-being and academic adjustment.

Underutilization of Professional Help

The comparatively low reliance on professional help (29% often, 31% very often) highlights barriers to seeking formal support. This finding resonates with Sreekanth et al. (2023), who reported that “although stress levels among adolescents were high, avoidance strategies predominated over professional help-seeking”. Possible explanations include stigma, lack of awareness, or limited availability of school counseling services. Strengthening mental health awareness and accessibility within schools may help overcome these barriers.

Presence of Maladaptive Coping

Despite the dominance of adaptive coping, strategies such as ignoring stress (69% combined often/very often) and not coping (70%) were also observed. These findings align with Carl, Jay, & Luzano (2024), who noted that “avoidance was a common but less functional coping method among students”. While such strategies may provide temporary relief, they do not “resolve underlying stressors and may predict poorer well-being outcomes” (Zammuner, 2019).

4. CONCLUSION

The analysis indicates that adolescents use a combination of coping strategies, with a marked preference for adaptive approaches such as problem-solving, social support, and recreational activities. However, reliance on self-blame, avoidance, and the low use of professional help suggest areas of concern. These findings call for school- and community-based interventions aimed at:

- Encouraging adaptive coping through problem-focused and social strategies,
- Promoting recreational and mindfulness activities, and
- Normalizing professional help-seeking behavior among adolescents.

Such efforts would enhance resilience and contribute to better academic and psychological outcomes during this critical developmental stage.

6. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

- To raise awareness of the value of coping mechanisms in children, the government may organise specific programs for educators, educational institutions, and parents.
- Other elements related to coping methods include organising and planning planned cultural events, maintaining consistency in home management, assisting the child in differentiating and being aware of himself, and enhancing the nature of discipline.
- Teachers are crucial to a child's education and growth. According to this study, children's academic performance is impacted by their coping mechanisms. Parents ought to be more conscious of their children's growth as well as the environment they offer at home. If children's academic performance is declining, they need to consider the various facets of coping mechanisms and look into which one needs to be addressed. Adopting a positive outlook and reframing challenging situations can help adolescents maintain motivation and resilience in the face of academic setbacks, ultimately leading to better academic outcomes.
- Engaging in activities that promote well-being, such as exercise, mindfulness, or hobbies, can help students manage stress and improve their overall mental and physical health, which are crucial for academic success.
- A similar study may be carried out on the students of different age group.
- A comparative study may be conducted on rural and urban students and with the type of family with the same variables.

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